

ORIGIN AND TREATMENT OF DEMODICOSIS DISEASE.

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Abstract: Today, skin diseases and their origin are very common. This article talks about demodicosis, its origin, clinical symptoms and treatment.

Key words: Demodex Folliculorum, demodex, parasite, dermatologist, Zenirit.

Most of us do not know what demodex is, and when it appears on the skin of beards that help with any miracle, it means advertising as an effective remedy for the problem. It surprises us when the magic remedies do not have the promised effect. If we consider this value in such cases, it is demodecosis, the cause of which is a completely imperceptible, small demodex egg. Demodex causes redness, irritation and damage to the skin. This discharge is provided by various substances in the sebaceous glands and eyelids.

Demodex is a dwarf, its size does not exceed two-thirds of a millimeter, and it is a parasite in the pus glands, as well as in the follicles of human hair. Despite the very small size of the flesh, a person infected with it suffers greatly from this parasite and lives with a feeling of discomfort and dissatisfaction with his appearance.

Demodex Folliculorum resides in hair follicles. It lives by sucking nutrients from the hair follicles and the hair itself, causing infection and swelling of the follicles, followed by general hair loss. These symptoms indicate that it is already time to consult a specialist. Demodex Brevis lives on the skin. It causes inflammation in the eyeball, face, and eardrum.

Symptoms of demodex

The symptoms of demodectic are simple enough and it is easy to determine if you are infected with this parasite or not. Demodex causes the appearance of red spots on the face and scalp and an increase in the amount of skin oils. In the same way, a person suffering from this infectious disease feels redness under the skin and itches. The condition of the skin worsens, it becomes "oily" and has an uneven appearance. The skin itself will be oily. The appearance of black spots indicates that the disease is getting worse and already has more effect on the skin. One of the symptoms of demodex is blepharitis - itching and redness of the eyelids. In the evening, these symptoms increase several times and require urgent treatment, because the condition of infected people may worsen and mucous discharge from the eyes can be observed.

Many patients begin to worry that the eyelashes partially fall out and white particles appear where they grow, it is possible to feel that there is something extra in the eye that causes discomfort.

If you find such signs, you need to analyze the demodex. It is best to get such an analysis from a dermatologist in a medical institution appointed. After receiving the test results, if you find out whether you are really infected with this parasite, the doctor will recommend you for further examinations.

The main reasons for the appearance of demodex eggs.

According to the results of the research, 97% of the population of the entire planet suffers from demodex, but when there is a favorable environment for this creature, life activity is activated

The most important reason for the activation of the subcutaneous parasite is the excessive use of facial cosmetics containing hormones. In addition, demodex can be activated due to the penetration of various bacteria on the skin through the affected areas of the skin on the face.

Redness and inflammation appear as a result of the laying of eggs by the demodex female. In general, the reasons for the spread of demodex are simple, but despite this, the problem remains very common and not everyone needs treatment.

According to the results of the analysis, if the presence of demodex is confirmed, the doctor will recommend you to be treated in a clinic, as a result of which you can save your home from the parasite. Your skin should not have excessive wounds and scars so that the treatment of demodicosis takes less time.

Most often, you prescribe the drug "Zenirit" for the treatment of demodex. The active substance of the drug is the antibiotic erythromycin, which is effective in fighting harmful bacteria, and also has an antiseptic effect. Zinerite also contains zinc, which helps reduce sebum production.

Experts also emphasize that the treatment should be carried out in difficult conditions, because demodex is very cunning, even after treatment it can return over time. In fact, parasite particles can remain in the objects of your daily life: sheets, towels, scars, and the risk of re-infection is very high after skin contact with these objects.

After you start treatment, get rid of these contacts or at least boil them and do it every time until you have a repeat analysis and know that you are healthy.

In addition, for the treatment of demodicosis, treatment with "Differin" in the form of a gel is effective, apply it once a day at bedtime. The treatment of DEMODEX disease, which has not found a cure in the world, has been started within 1-2 months through natural creams and masks made for Demadecosis by TK Corporation.

For the treatment of facial skin, experts recommend using "tar tar" soap, which should be washed daily. Washing it in water does not give good results, washing it with tincture of flowers or raisins gives good results. Over time, you will notice that the face returns to its original state, becomes softer and has a healthy appearance.

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